

The Cosmic Seed : Revisiting the Panspermia Hypothesis

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1. Preface

Throughout history, scientists have debated about the origins of life. Several theories were proposed after experimentation and hypotheses from famous scholars. These include the Primordial Soup Theory, which suggests that life began in a 'soup' of organic molecules, possibly in the oceans or other bodies of water, catalyzed by various energy sources like lightning or ultraviolet light it starts to fold into complex structures and later into the four macromolecules that formed the building blocks of the cell-basic units of life. The Hydrothermal Vent Theory is another similar theory that suggests life originated at hydrothermal vents on the ocean floor, where mineral-laden water provides a rich source of chemicals. The last and most important is the cosmic theory, stating that life did not originate on earth, instead it was brought here from elsewhere in the universe, possibly by comets, meteorites, or interstellar dust in the form of spores called 'cosmoza'. Within the three theories, I believe the cosmic theory should be supported due to existing scientific proof in nature, the logical existence of life in space, and that the other theories only relied on experimental evidence and have instances of logical and scientific flaws.

2. The cosmic theory-Reasons of being the most important

Firstly, the cosmic theory is the only theory that has logical evidence that exists in nature. An important example of this is the ALH84001 meteorite. Discovered in 1984, this space object has been suspected to contain life. The State University of Florida established a study that examined fragments of rock chip, 270 (parent, 221) from the meteorite ALH84001 and discovered the presence of magnetite crystal chains at a uniform size and shape [1]. This indicates that these chains could only be produced by biogenesis instead of inorganic processes, indicating evidence for the presence of life on space objects that landed on Earth. Moreover, this study also suggests that the crystals found on the meteorite resemble modern magnetotactic bacteria. This proves that the bacteria on Earth are also found on interstellar objects, further indicating the cosmic hypothe-

sis. Besides direct fossils of microorganism life, building blocks of life were also discovered on those meteorites. Recently, Yoshihiro Furukawa, a geochemist at Tohoku University in Sendai, Japan, and colleagues found ribose, along with several chemically similar sugars, in samples from two meteorites, one collected from Morocco and the other from Australia [2]. Ribose is the necessary building block for the nucleic acid RNA, which forms the backbone of RNA, necessary for gene coding, decoding, regulation, and expression. Ribose is involved in cellular energy transfer, notably in ATP formation, crucial for cellular functions. Additionally, ribose participates in signaling pathways through compounds like cAMP and is integral to metabolism and nucleotide biosynthesis, highlighting its fundamental role in genetic and cellular processes. Ribose exerts a great function in the development of life. With the existence of such a macromolecule on the meteorite, it would be possible that these organic building blocks landed on Earth from outer space and formed into life on Earth.

3. Supporting evidence

Secondly, the survival of life in space is logically and experimentally proven. The first criticisms that come to people's minds against the cosmic theory are the doubt about whether life can survive the harsh conditions of space. Experimental evidence has proved the possibility of microorganism survival in space and the possibility of space travel [3] The LICHENS experiment conducted by ESA on the Foton-M2 mission revealed that lichens could survive the harsh conditions of open space, including vacuum, temperature fluctuations, solar UV radiation, and cosmic radiation for up to two weeks [4]. Lichens were known for their symbiotic relations with plants and are often considered complex organisms in nature. Such complex organisms like the lichen could survive this period in space is a good indication that the space environment may not be completely fatal for all organisms. This is also proven with longer surviving times of simpler microorganisms: The study published in "Scientific Reports" demonstrated that microorganisms, including spore-forming bacteria *Bacillus subtilis*, fungi *Aureobasidium pullulans*, and archaea *Methanosarcina mazei* S-6 T, can survive two years of exposure in outer space near

the International Space Station (ISS) [5]. This survival was attributed to dehydration and partial lyophilization in the vacuum of near-Earth space, suggesting the robust nature of these microorganisms against extreme space conditions. Moreover, research has shown that clumps of *Deinococcus* bacteria can survive for three years when exposed to the International Space Station's outer surface [6]. These bacteria form protective balls, with outer layers shielding the inner microbes from space extremes. The discovery of these simple microorganisms that had developed strong adaptations to survive in the space environment provides solid evidence for the cosmic theory that the first life forms on Earth like stromatolites could have landed on Earth through these meteorites, and even if they did not come in that way, the meteorites could still bring life with their heavy contents of macromolecules like ribose.

4. The Key

The key for the cosmic theory to stand out from other theories is that it contains fewer logical flaws and can stand more criticism compared to other theories. Compared to the cosmic theory, other theories lacked solid supportive evidence and reasoning. The chemical evolution theory, or the Primordial Soup Theory suggests that life began in a "primordial soup" of organic molecules in the early Earth's oceans, under a reducing atmosphere (one lacking oxygen). However, with the theoretical proof like the Miller-Urey Experiment that organic molecules can be formed under such conditions, the theory itself has a major logical flaw. It proposes that macromolecules had been formed in the ocean. The formation of these macromolecules requires dehydration or condensation reactions, which is not favorable in the presence of water [6]. Instead, water would facilitate the hydrolysis reactions that tend to break down these polymers back into their monomers. Similar to the chemical evolution theory, the hydrothermal vent theory proposed the formation of life under similar conditions in the deep ocean. Comparatively, the cosmic theory is less afraid of criticism. The main criticisms of the cosmic theory focus on the survival of life in outer space and the persistence of the forms of life during its transportation in space or the landing on Earth. Some argue that space is filled with high levels of radiation, including cosmic rays, which can damage or destroy organic molecules, making it hard for those life forms to persist in space. However, previous evidence of the LICHENS experiment and studies around the *Deinococcus* bacteria have proved that simple life forms can survive up to three years in space, and even complex life like lichens can survive up to two weeks. Even if these forms of organisms are still considered advanced or complicated for survival and transportation in space, there is still existing evidence of simpler molecules like ribose that are present on meteorites, suggesting an existing possibility of life coming

from space. Most importantly, the cosmic theory is one of the only theories that possesses evidence in nature instead of only in laboratories. Conditions in the lab cannot reconstruct the real environment of nature where life has formed. The existence of evidence for this theory in nature provides it with the most possibility.

5. Ending Remarks

Throughout long periods, scientists have debated about how life originated. Even with rational and logical theories such as the Cosmic theory, one important point of the logic is still unfilled for most of these theories: does life even originate in the first place? The Chemical evolution theory and the hydrothermal vent theories give a logical explanation of the formation of the building blocks of life but illogical statements of the synthesis of complex life forms. Although the cosmic theory provides a very logical argument about the arrival and transportation of life to Earth, it still does not answer the question of where life comes from. For this logical point to be clarified, more discoveries would need to be made. However, if we focus on current theories and knowledge, the cosmic theory is still the best theory due to its existing natural evidence of biological remains on meteorites and the evidence that life can survive and travel in space.

References

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